

Resistance Spot Welding of HSLA 340 Automotive Steel: Process Parameters, Weld Quality, and Finite Element Simulation—A Review

Mr. Sumit V. Tiwari¹, Prof. R. M. Choudhari², Prof. P. V. Chopde³, Dr. Y. A. Kharche⁴

¹ PG Student, Mechanical Engineering, Padm. Dr. V. B. Kolte College of Engineering, Malkapur, India

^{2,3} Assistant Professor, Mechanical Engineering, Padm. Dr. V. B. Kolte College of Engineering, Malkapur, India

⁴ Associate Professor, Mechanical Engineering, Padm. Dr. V. B. Kolte College of Engineering, Malkapur, India

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19334833

ABSTRACT

High-strength low-alloy (HSLA) steels, such as HSLA 340, account for a great part of the construction of vehicle bodies and structures because of high strength-to-weight ratio combined with good formability. For these steels, use of resistance spot welding (RSW) as the joining method is the prevailing technique. But weld quality and joint performance are highly dependent on process parameters. In this review, we critically examine the existing literature on resistance spot welding of HSLA, along with comparable automotive steels. We focus then on process parameters, weld quality, microstructural evolution, mechanical behavior, and finite element simulation approaches. The review demonstrates the effect of welding current, welding time, and electrode force on heat input, nugget formation, and failure modes and states that weld nugget size is the most important parameter which governs tensile shear strength. Fusion zone and heat-affected zone microstructural changes and related hardness changes are found to play an important role in fracture behaviour. While there is a well-established experimental literature for advanced high-strength and dual-phase steels, HSLA 340 is not consistently well represented in experimental and numerical studies. Additionally, resistance spot welding finite element modeling is limited by simplistic assumptions and there is a lack of validation for a specific material. A definite gap is identified in the review: the current study does not identify an unmet need for integrated experimental–numerical model systems to systematically optimize RSW parameters for HSLA 340 steel. By investigating this gap of knowledge by performing coupled electro-thermal-mechanical finite element analysis, we can anticipate increasing accuracy for predicting weld quality, minimizing experimental effort, and increasing joint reliability in automobile manufacturing.

Keywords: - Resistance spot welding; HSLA 340 steel; Welding parameter optimization; Weld nugget formation; Finite element analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

It is a continual quest of the automotive industry to minimize vehicles' weight while retaining structural integrity and cost-effectiveness. This has resulted in its widespread usage as the body-in-white and structural car parts and high-strength low-alloy (HSLA) steels, including types such as HSLA 340. Compared to non-HSLA steels, HSLA steels have high strength, good formability, and good weldability which is one factor to suit automotive production on large scale. Of these different joining methods, resistance spot welding (RSW) is the most common because of its high productivity, simplicity of automation, and compatibility to sheet metal assembly. Most important in the quality and efficiency of the resistance spot-welds are the process parameters, including welding current, welding time, electrode force, and electrode geometry. Such parameters direct heat generation at the faying interface, nugget growth, and behavior toward solidification and have a direct effect on the mechanical performance of assembly. Early studies [1] from Aslanlar indicated that the size of weld nugget is paramount in defining the mechanical characteristics of the spot welded joints, establishing a basic connection between welding parameters and joint strength.

Since that time extensive experimental research into the effect with respect to quality and mechanical performance of different automotive steels has been performed to know how RSW parameters affect welds quality as well as the mechanical properties are affected. Ding et al. [2] also found that enhanced welding current and its time yield better tensile shear strength in resistance spot-welded TWIP steel under a regulated condition by the controlled formation of nugget. Similarly, Chen et al. [3] studied how the welding current and

welding time affect the shearing strength of distinct steel joints, and concluded that the performance of a joint is sensitive to the choice of process window. Based on comparison studies with self-piercing riveting, RSW and alternative joining methods have further highlighted the need for optimization in order to attain exceptional joint performance in automotive galvanized steels [4].

Microstructural evolution within the fusion zone (FZ) and heat-affected zone (HAZ) is another critical factor affecting weld integrity. Studies on advanced high-strength steels have shown that welding parameters influence martensite formation, hardness distribution, and fracture behavior [6], [9], [12]. Rajarajan et al. [9] demonstrated that electrode force significantly affects nugget size, microstructural refinement, and tensile shear strength, while Rajarajan et al. [12] further correlated fracture modes with microstructural features in resistance spot-welded dual-phase steel joints. Advanced failure mechanisms, including liquid metal embrittlement and fatigue-related damage, have also been reported in spot-welded joints under tensile shear loading [15], [16].

As dissimilar steel combinations and automotive structures are increasingly used, resistance spot welding has become an increasingly intricate topic to explore. In the domain of dissimilar steel joints such as DP1000HF/CP800, stainless steel combinations, and tailor hot-stamped assemblies, extensive investigations have detected the characteristics of nugget asymmetry, uneven heat distribution, as well as premature failure modes [7], [8], [13], [14]. The importance of accurate control of welding parameters to achieve desired joint performance across different material systems is also emphasized by these studies.

Experimental studies give important information in process–structure–property relationships, but they are frequently constrained by the high cost, extensive trial requirements, and inability to model transient thermal, electrical, and mechanical interactions during welding. To overcome these limitations, finite element analysis (FEA) has been proposed as a suitable method to simulate the RSW process. Numerical modeling enables prediction of temperature distribution, nugget growth, contact resistance evolution, and mechanical response of welded joints. Shome & Chatterjee [20] proved the effect of properties of material and contact resistance on size formation of nuggets, and Matsushita et al. [18] emphasized the importance of modern systems for current and force control to enhance weld quality.

While the existing literature specifically on resistance spot welding for advanced high-strength and dual-phase steels is vast, there has been limited comprehensive review studies conducted on HSLA steels, particularly HSLA 340. Previous studies generalize the results across different grades of steel without summarizing and evaluating HSLA steels in the context of finite element modeling tools for optimizing parameters. Similarly, differences among the reported optimal welding windows, mechanical performance, and modeling assumptions demand a systematic synthesis of experimental and numerical studies.

Therefore, this study will perform a critical review and synthesis of literature on resistance spot welding of HSLA 340 and similar automotive steels based on process parameters, weld quality, microstructural evolution, mechanical behavior, and finite element simulation approaches. This review is, therefore, conducted to investigate the relevant challenges experienced, knowledge gaps, and future research directions in RSW of HSLA steels for advanced automotive manufacturing by connecting experimental findings and numerical modeling perspectives.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Fundamentals of Resistance Spot Welding and Nugget Formation

Resistance spot welding (RSW) is a thermo-electrical joining process that uses heat produced by electrical resistance at the faying interface to melt the metal and produce the nugget in the melted area. So, the mechanical performance of spot-welded joints is highly sensitive to the size, shape, and integrity of the weld nugget. Aslanlar [1] is one of the first and important researchers to systematically demonstrate the direct effect of nugget diameter on tensile shear strength and failure mode of steel sheets in the spot-welded automotive context. Insufficient nugget size leads to interfacial failure and excess heat input may drive expulsion and electrode degradation, the study noted.

Weld nugget formation and growth are dictated by welding current, welding time, electrode force, and contact resistance. Shome and Chatterjee [20] showed that material characteristics and surface properties strongly influence contact resistance, consequently affecting heat generation and nugget size. As a result, the results confirm that in order to achieve a consistent weld quality, control over both the processing parameters and material properties is critical.

2.2 Effect of Welding Parameters on Mechanical Properties

The mechanical behaviour of resistance spot welds in automotive steels has been studied variously depending on the welding conditions. Ding et al. [2] have adopted a combination of empirical studies and numerical simulations to improve tensile shear strength of TWIP steel spot welds. Their results demonstrated that optimized welding current and time promote stable nugget growth and improve load-bearing capacity.

Chen et al. [3] studied the influence of welding current and welding time on the shear strength of dissimilar steel joints and found a significant dependence of joint strength on heat input. The same phenomena were noted for dual-phase and advanced high-strength steels, where incorrect parameter selection caused expulsion or undersized nuggets, weakening joint strength [21], [22].

Another important parameter has been shown to be the electrode force. Rajarajan et al. [9] emphasized that increasing electrode force promotes contact conditions and thus nugget consistency, and excessive force suppresses nugget growth by reducing contact resistance. These results reflect the interplay between welding parameters and joint performance.

2.3 Microstructural Evolution and Failure Behavior

Microstructural changes occurring in the fusion zone (FZ) and heat-affected zone (HAZ) significantly influence weld strength and fracture behavior. Studies on advanced high-strength steels have shown that rapid heating and cooling during RSW lead to martensitic transformation in the fusion zone, resulting in high hardness but potential brittleness [6], [12].

Rajarajan *et al.* [12] correlated microstructural features with tensile shear fracture modes and observed that failure location shifts from interfacial to pull-out mode with increasing nugget size and improved microstructural uniformity. Jia *et al.* [10] further reported that welding parameters influence hardness gradients across the weld, affecting load transfer during mechanical testing.

Advanced failure mechanisms such as liquid metal embrittlement (LME) have also been reported in resistance spot welds. Siar *et al.* [15] employed three-dimensional characterization techniques to study crack propagation during tensile shear testing and revealed that LME-induced cracks initiate in the heat-affected zone and propagate along grain boundaries. Fatigue-related degradation in spot welds has also been linked to microhardness variation and phase transformation [16].

2.4 Resistance Spot Welding of Dissimilar and Advanced Steels

With the increasing use of multi-material automotive structures, resistance spot welding of dissimilar steels has received increasing attention. Kekik et al. [7] studied RSW of DP1000HF/CP800 steel joints and pointed out the asymmetric formation of the nugget and the stress distribution that is not consistent because of the differences in material properties. The same problems were also encountered in dissimilar stainless steel joints where differences in electrical and thermal conductivity contributed to different nugget morphology and joint strength [14].

Based on comparative studies with RSW and other joining techniques like self-piercing riveting, we identified that although RSW provides joint stiffness and strength, its performance becomes extremely sensitive to parameter optimization, making them particularly relevant on galvanized and coated steels [4]. Tailor hot-stamped assemblies had further investigations that uncovered detailed failure modes under impact loading, emphasizing the importance of design of suitable welds [8].

2.5 Finite Element Modeling and Process Simulation

Experimental analysis of RSW is often restricted by the high cost and difficulty in capturing transient thermal–electrical–mechanical interactions. To address these limitations, finite element analysis (FEA) has been extensively used in modeling the RSW process. Numerical simulations may predict the temperature distribution, nugget growth, contact resistance evolution, and residual stress development.

Matsushita et al. [18] developed advanced current and electrode force control strategies using numerical modeling to improve weld quality in single-side resistance spot welding. Májlinger et al. [11] developed predictive models based on the geometry of weld and the physical properties of the material to predict tensile shear strength of spot-welded steel sheets and found a reasonable agreement with experimental studies.

It has been demonstrated in FEA studies that accurate simulations of contact resistance, material properties, and phase transformation behavior are indispensable for proper prediction of nugget size and mechanical performance [20], [24]. These modelling methods contribute useful guidance for process optimization and reduction of experimental trials.

2.6 Research Gaps Related to HSLA 340 Steel

Although resistance spot welding for high-strength and dual-phase steels has been well-studied in the literature, work has been scarce on HSLA steels, particularly HSLA 340. The literature tends to apply common welding techniques to different steels with little reference to the specific thermal and mechanical behavior of HSLA steels [17]. Additionally, there are few attempts to incorporate experimental results with finite element simulations for systematic parameter optimization in HSLA steels.

Differences in reported optimal welding windows, nugget size criteria, and failure mechanisms also point to the need for a comprehensive synthesis of experimental and numerical studies focused on HSLA steels.

Table 1 Literature-Based Analysis of Process–Structure–Property Relationships in Resistance Spot Welding

Theme	Key References	What Has Been Studied	Key Outcomes	Limitations Identified	Research Gap
Nugget size vs mechanical strength	[1], [2], [9], [11]	Relationship between nugget diameter and tensile shear strength	Larger nugget improves strength; expulsion at high heat input	Mostly experimental; limited grade-specific focus	Need nugget–strength correlation for HSLA 340 using simulation
Effect of welding current & time	[2], [3], [10], [21]	Influence of current and time on joint strength and hardness	Optimal heat input critical for strength	Narrow parameter windows; trial-and-error based	FEA-based optimization for HSLA steels lacking
Effect of electrode force	[9], [18], [20]	Contact resistance and nugget consistency studied	Higher force improves stability up to a limit	Force–current coupling rarely modeled	Coupled electro-thermal-mechanical models needed
Microstructural evolution (FZ & HAZ)	[6], [10], [12], [16]	Phase transformation, hardness distribution, fracture behavior	Martensitic FZ dominates strength & failure	Mostly qualitative microstructure analysis	Quantitative microstructure–property linkage for HSLA 340
Failure modes & fracture behavior	[1], [8], [12], [15]	Interfacial vs pull-out failure, LME, fatigue cracking	Failure mode depends on nugget & HAZ	Limited predictive capability	Failure mode prediction via FEA not explored
Dissimilar steel spot welding	[3], [4], [7], [14], [22]	Nugget asymmetry and material mismatch effects	Heat imbalance affects strength	HSLA steels rarely included	HSLA-to-AHSS dissimilar welding unexplored
Comparison with alternative joining	[4], [5]	RSW vs SPR / TIG-spot welding	RSW superior if optimized	No numerical justification	Simulation-based comparative studies absent
Finite element modeling of RSW	[2], [11], [18], [20]	Thermal and strength prediction models	Good agreement with experiments	Simplified assumptions; limited HSLA data	HSLA 340-specific coupled FEA models needed
Control strategies & optimization	[18], [11]	Current and force control strategies	Improved weld consistency	No AI/optimization frameworks	Scope for optimization algorithms + FEA
HSLA steel-specific studies	[17]	Parameter optimization for HSLA 355	Improved joint strength	No transient thermal or stress modeling	Direct scope for HSLA 340 modeling & valid

Based on the analysis of existing literature that is presented in Table 1, the weld nugget size is the most significant factor in determining the tensile shear strength and failure mode of resistance spot-welded automotive steels. Although the welding current and welding time have a major influence on heat input and nugget growth, the optimal parameter window is narrow and strongly material dependent. Electrode force has substantial influence over both contact resistance and nugget consistency, but its combined effect with welding current is generally neglected. Microstructural evolution within the fusion zone and heat-affected zone is of paramount importance for hardness distribution, mechanical properties, and fracture behavior, for which we observe an interfacial to pull-out failure mode depending on nugget size. In dissimilar welds between different steels, there is a particular importance in resistance spot welding because the nugget will not be uniform and heat distributed less evenly as a result of the nature of the different materials. Most papers have been experimental work, but limited finite element–based studies have been reported, as shown in Table 1, which usually focus on simplified assumptions. Significantly, HSLA steels, especially HSLA 340, are under-represented in both experimental and numerical studies. On the whole, the absence of integrated experimental–numerical methods of parameter optimization, as revealed by Table 1, means a definite knowledge gap and stimulates the search for finite element–assisted optimization of the resistance spot welding parameters for HSLA 340 automotive steel.

Chart -1 Thematic Mapping of Existing Literature on HSLA Steel Welding Characteristics

As illustrated in Chart 1, the current landscape of RSW research exhibits a significant concentration on dissimilar steel joining and failure mode analysis. The bar chart categorizes cited literature to emphasize the relative maturity of experimental themes versus numerical modeling themes. Notably, the scarcity of references for "HSLA steel-specific studies" highlights a critical deficiency in the existing body of work. This visual data supports the study's objective to address the identified gaps in HSLA 340 specific parameters. Thus, Chart 1 serves as a quantitative justification for the proposed development of coupled FEA models and optimization frameworks.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Resistance spot welding continues to be an important joining process for automotive sheet steels, and its utility depends on the combination of process condition, welding nugget generation, microstructural development, and mechanical function. The literature identified shows that welding current, welding time, and electrode force are paramount in regulating heat input, nugget size, and joint strength, with nugget diameter identified as the main factor influencing tensile shear performance and failure mode.

Microstructural transitions in the fusion region and heat-affected region have a significant effect on hardness distribution and fracture behavior, especially the change between interfacial failure and pull-out failure modes. The extensive experimental literature has been published on high-strength and dual-phase steels, but there is little work focused on HSLA steels, especially HSLA 340. Additionally, the majority of current research relies on experimental trial-and-error methods, and finite element-based modeling and simulation applications are limited and often made by using simplified assumptions, with no material-specific validation. The review suggests the absence of an integrated experimental-numerical design pipeline that can systematically optimize resistance spot welding parameters and predict weld quality and failure behavior.

In summary, there is a distinct requirement for in-depth studies to fuse experimental characterization with coupled electro-thermal-mechanical finite element analysis for optimal resistance spot welding parameters for HSLA 340 automotive steel. Such a single solution is fundamental for achieving an efficient weld, decreasing development time, and for improving the reliability of the joint in contemporary automotive industry.

4. REFERENCES

- [1] A. Aslanlar, "The effect of nucleus size on mechanical properties in electrical resistance spot welding of sheets used in automotive industry," *Materials & Design*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 125–131, 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2004.09.025.
- [2] K. Ding, Y. Wang, M. Lei, T. Wei, G. Wu, Y. Zhang, and Y. Gao, "Numerical and experimental investigations on the enhancement of the tensile shear strength for resistance spot welded TWIP steel," *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, vol. 76, pp. 365–378, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jmapro.2022.02.031.
- [3] L. Chen, Y. Zhang, X. Xue, B. Wang, J. Yang, Z. Zhang, and G. C. Barber, "Investigation on shearing strength of resistance spot-welded joints of dissimilar steel plates with varying welding current and time," *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, vol. 16, pp. 1021–1028, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jmrt.2021.12.079.
- [4] B. Asati, N. Shajan, A. K. VT, K. S. Arora, and R. G. Narayanan, "A comparative investigation on self-piercing riveting and resistance spot welding of automotive grade dissimilar galvanized steel sheets," *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 123, no. 3–4, pp. 1079–1097, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s00170-022-10226-y.
- [5] B. Rajak, K. Kishore, and V. Mishra, "Investigation of a novel TIG-spot welding vis-à-vis resistance spot welding of DP590 steel: Processing-microstructure-mechanical properties correlation," *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, vol. 296, p. 127254, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.matchemphys.2022.127254.

- [6] T. Das, S. K. Panda, K. S. Arora, and J. Paul, "Investigation of the microstructure and mechanical behaviour of resistance spot-welded CR210 steel joints using graphene as an interlayer," *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, vol. 302, p. 127693, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.matchemphys.2023.127693.
- [7] M. Kekik, F. Özen, V. Onar, and S. Aslanlar, "Investigation effect of resistance spot welding parameters on dissimilar DP1000HF/CP800 steel joints," *Sādhanā*, vol. 47, no. 4, p. 203, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s12046-022-01977-1.
- [8] C. Tolton, C. O'Keeffe, A. Mohammadzadeh, J. Imbert, and M. Worswick, "Investigation of resistance spot weld failure in tailor hot stamped assemblies," *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, p. 104677, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ijimpeng.2023.104677.
- [9] C. Rajarajan, T. Sonar, P. Sivaraj, S. Raja, and N. Mathiazhagan, "Effect of electrode pressure on nugget size, microstructure and tensile shear strength of resistance spot welded dual-phase steel joints," *Metallography, Microstructure, and Analysis*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 472–483, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s13632-022-00862-x.
- [10] X. Jia, S. Wei, and S. Lu, "Investigation on microstructure and tensile shear properties of strengthened steel resistance spot welded joint," *Science and Technology of Welding and Joining*, vol. 28, no. 8, pp. 810–818, 2023, doi: 10.1080/13621718.2023.2233174.
- [11] K. Májlínger, L. T. Katula, and B. Varbai, "Prediction of the shear tension strength of resistance spot welded thin steel sheets from high- to ultrahigh-strength range," *Periodica Polytechnica Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 66, no. 1, pp. 67–82, 2022, doi: 10.3311/PPme.18934.
- [12] C. Rajarajan, P. Sivaraj, T. Sonar, S. Raja, and N. Mathiazhagan, "Microstructural features and tensile shear fracture properties of resistance spot welded advanced high-strength dual-phase steel sheets," *Journal of Mechanical Behavior of Materials*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 52–63, 2022, doi: 10.1515/jmbm-2022-0006.
- [13] M. Prabhakaran, D. Jeyasimman, and M. Varatharajulu, "Investigation of the failure mechanism of dissimilar resistance spot welding of steels," *Emerging Materials Research*, vol. 40, pp. 1–9, 2023, doi: 10.1680/jemmr.22.00224.
- [14] S. Midhun, C. Ramesh, K. Chellamuthu, and R. Yokeswaran, "Dissimilar resistance spot welding of AISI 304 and AISI 202," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 69, pp. 1213–1217, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2022.08.262.
- [15] O. Siar, S. Dancette, J. Adrien, T. Dupuy, and D. Fabrègue, "3D characterization of liquid metal embrittlement crack propagation during tensile shear testing of resistance spot welds," *Materials Characterization*, vol. 184, p. 111664, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.matchar.2021.111664.
- [16] T. Tian, W. Tao, and S. Yang, "Microhardness and fatigue life of spot welded quenching and partitioning 1180 steel," *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, vol. 19, pp. 3145–3159, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jmrt.2022.06.083.
- [17] R. M. Choudhari, A. M. Adhaye, V. N. Sulakhe, P. S. Warke, and K. G. Maniyar, "Analysis of tensile strength and performance of resistance spot welding parameters for HSLA 355 steel," *Journal of Mines, Metals and Fuels*, vol. 73, no. 5, pp. 1409–1418, 2025, doi: 10.18311/jmmf/2025/48684.
- [18] M. Matsushita, R. Ikeda, and K. Oi, "Development of a new program control setting of welding current and electrode force for single-side resistance spot welding," *International Journal of Materials Joining*, vol. 59, no. 4, pp. 533–543, 2015, doi: 10.1007/s40194-015-0228-1.
- [19] S. H. Arabi, M. Pouranvari, and M. Movahedi, "Pathways to improve austenite–ferrite phase balance during resistance spot welding of duplex stainless steels," *Science and Technology of Welding and Joining*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 8–15, 2019, doi: 10.1080/13621718.2018.1468949.
- [20] M. Shome and S. Chatterjee, "Effect of material properties on contact resistance and nugget size during spot welding of low carbon coated steels," *ISIJ International*, vol. 49, no. 9, pp. 1384–1391, 2009, doi: 10.2355/isijinternational.49.1384.
- [21] S. Aktas, U. Ozsarac, and S. Aslanlar, "Effect of spot welding parameters on tensile properties of DP600 steel sheet joints," *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, vol. 27, no. 7, pp. 756–764, 2012, doi: 10.1080/10426914.2011.647940.
- [22] H. Aydin, "Mechanical properties of dissimilar resistance spot-welded DP600–DP1000 steel joints for automotive applications," *Proceedings of the IMechE, Part D: Journal of Automobile Engineering*, 2014, doi: 10.1177/0954407014547749.
- [23] K. Kishore, P. Kumar, and G. Mukhopadhyay, "Resistance spot weldability of galvanized and bare DP600 steel," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 271, pp. 237–248, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2019.04.005.
- [24] S. T. Wei *et al.*, "Similar and dissimilar resistance spot welding of advanced high strength steels: Welding and heat treatment procedures, structure and mechanical properties," *Science and Technology of Welding and Joining*, vol. 19, no. 5, pp. 427–435, 2014, doi: 10.1179/1362171814Y.0000000211.